

CONSUMER PERCEPTION AND ACCEPTANCE OF BIO-BASED PACKAGING: INSIGHTS FROM A QUALITATIVE STUDY

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Abstract: *In the face of growing resource scarcity and socio-environmental concerns, more sustainable packaging solutions are becoming increasingly important, especially under the European Green Deal and the new Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR). Although consumers are showing a growing interest in recycling and environmentally friendly packaging, they often find it difficult to properly assess sustainability. Most of them cannot distinguish between materials such as recycled, biodegradable, and bio-based plastics, because they are not always visually recognizable. This qualitative study, namely focus group discussions, investigates consumer perception and acceptance of bio-based packaging, underlining the importance of acceptance for successful market introduction. An extensive literature review was carried out to develop the discussion guideline and to identify keywords, which were used as anchor points for the analysis. In addition, product samples were presented to the participants to assess their perception of sustainable packaging. The results show that consumers evaluate sustainable packaging mainly based on color and material. Although they appreciate sustainability claims, consumers want them to be easy to understand. The design should not be too novel and should align with brand recognition, as well as price and quality of the product. Overall, consumers are still reluctant to pay significantly more for sustainable packaging. This is why clearly communicating the added value is essential for achieving wider acceptance. Based on these findings, the study provides recommendations for design and consumer communication to foster acceptance of bio-based packaging and support a successful market launch.*

Keywords: consumer perceptions, qualitative consumer research, consumer decision criteria for sustainable packaging, focus group discussion, bio-based packaging

1 INTRODUCTION

In view of resource scarcity, stricter regulatory requirements, and growing socio-ecological challenges, the development of more sustainable packaging solutions is becoming increasingly important, as emphasized by the European Green Deal and the new EU Packaging and PPWR (European Commission, 2019; European Parliament and Council, 2025). At the same time, consumer awareness is rising, reflected in a significant increase in interest in recycling and sustainably produced materials (Rietz and Kremel, 2023; Herbes, Beuthner and Ramme, 2018). In this context, it is imperative to understand consumer acceptance of sustainable packaging, as despite the growing interest and significant efforts from academia and industry, a gap persists between interest and the actual acceptance of sustainable alternatives. Based on authors' experience, transparent cellulose-based film packaging is often not

considered to be more sustainable than plastic-based film packaging. Consumers often find it challenging to distinguish between recycled and biodegradable materials and to assess the sustainability of packaging. Even bio-based plastic, which can have the potential to be less impactful on the environment than fossil-based plastic, is not always identifiable as such (Magnier and Schoormans, 2017). Whilst features, such as natural colours (e.g. green or brown), rough textures (Otto et al., 2021), images of animals or flowers (for cosmetics and household care products), and labels referencing nature and ecological sustainability (Robertson, 2013), are noticed, the ecological added value of alternative packaging remains unclear to consumers. Consequently, conventional packaging is often preferred. Against this backdrop, research into the acceptance of sustainable packaging solutions, particularly bio-based ones, and their design options, is becoming increasingly important.

The EU project BioSupPack aims to demonstrate a process for the production and enzymatic recycling of environmentally safe, superior, and versatile polyhydroxyalkanoate-based rigid packaging solutions by plasma integration in the value chain. BioSupPack's purpose is to upscale innovative, economically convenient and highly-performing bio-based rigid packaging solutions which are also suitable for being recycled and recovered. The results of this qualitative consumer study will be taken into account in the development of innovative packaging in order to increase market acceptance. The project encompasses a diverse range of applications, including food and household packaging. In addition to the functional, ecological, social and economic aspects, the consumer perception is considered, given that acceptance is one of the key factors in the success of packaging innovations. This study assesses consumer understanding of sustainability, focusing on consumers' expectations on circular bio-based packaging. The focus is on the following questions: (1) Which selection criteria do consumers use and which information needs do they have regarding sustainable packaging in the cosmetics, household goods, food and beverages product groups? (2) How do consumers evaluate the new bio-based packaging in comparison to non-bio-based benchmark packaging?

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

In February 2025, four focus group discussions were conducted to investigate how consumers perceive and accept new bio-based packaging compared to non-bio-based reference packaging. This method was chosen because focus group discussions allow for the collection of in-depth insights into consumer attitudes and perceptions that would not emerge in standardized surveys or individual interviews. The discussions took place in the designated test area at Mangold's Video Observation Laboratory of the University Albstadt-Sigmaringen, which complies with ISO 8589 standards, ensuring a controlled and professional environment. Each discussion lasted approximately 90 minutes. Recruitment was carried out using convenience sampling method, a non-random sampling method whereby participants were selected because they were available at the time. Only consumers aged 18 to 70, who regularly purchase conventional products and are interested in the topics of packaging, transparency, and sustainability, were considered. People, who do not deal with packaged products, as well as professionals from the packaging industry or related fields, were excluded. In total, 16 consumers participated in the four focus group discussions. The focus group discussions were audio- and video-recorded and were transcribed using an AI-supported transcription system (AI based transcription in Mangold INTERACT and descript). The structuring of the focus group discussions was based on keywords. Building on previous research (e.g., Otto et al., 2021), a comprehensive literature review was conducted, from which the most relevant keywords for the study were identified and selected. This resulted in a set of keywords (i.e., credibility, transparency, individuality, relevance, the novelty factor, sustainability, packaging, price, and bio-based materials) that served as a common thread throughout the discussion and as anchor points for the analysis. The participants in the study were not given an explicit definition of the individual key words to not influence their perception and interpretation.

The text material was analyzed qualitatively using a predefined evaluation scheme. The evaluation process consisted of manually identifying the most important information from the discussions. The procedure contains fixed criteria for identifying key sentences containing the keywords and is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Procedure for identifying key sentences within qualitative consumer research.

In addition to generating text material, image material was also collected within the study to determine which visual and haptic criteria are relevant to consumers. To this end, two sorting tasks were carried out at the beginning of the focus group discussions to gather initial assessments of the packaging to sustainability from the four categories. First, participants were separated in two small groups, in which each was asked to select two packages from a mixed set of prototypes and commercially available packaging. Group 1 had to select the two packages perceived to be the most sustainable, while Group 2 had to select the two perceived to be the least sustainable. Then, the four selected packages were discussed and ranked together on a scale from “less sustainable” to “sustainable”. In a second sorting process, participants select packages within a product group (food, beverages, cosmetics, or household goods) to capture context-specific differences, with the sorting again ranging from “sustainable” to “less sustainable”. For the purpose of evaluation, the packaging that was rated as particularly sustainable or particularly unsustainable by all groups was compared with each other in order to identify possible similarities (see figure 3).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

On the one hand, the manual analysis of key sentences reveals that consumers tend to prefer unique and individual designs for cosmetics packaging. On the other hand, food, household goods, and beverages should be packaged more simply with easily recognizable sustainability features. The findings demonstrate that consumers have a desire to be able to identify and purchase their customary products. Packaging should enable consumers to easily recognize products, among other things, to facilitate product selection (Robertson, 2013). The product is more important than the packaging, as evidenced by the fact that some participants said that “different-looking packaging signals a change, but the most important thing is that the contents remain the same.” Furthermore, unconventional designs have the potential to attract consumers' attention, yet they may also perplex consumers and potentially dissuade them from making a purchase (Bauer et al., 2023). Regarding packaging size, large packages are perceived as more sustainable than single servings, according to the results of the focus group discussion. For example, participants in the focus group discussions explained that “if there is little product inside, it is likely to be used up more quickly and you have to buy another package soon,” so this result contradicts the findings presented in the study of Bauer et al. (2023). The discrepancy in the results may be due to the fact that the comparable study focused on food waste, whereas our study focused on the use of packaging materials in relation to the product. Sustainability can be

assessed differently depending on the perspective. Studies by Tapiola et al. (2023) and Bauer et al. (2023) show, that although packaging size is a selection criterion, oversized packaging is considered less sustainable because it can lead to food waste (Tapiola et al., 2023; Bauer et al., 2023).

Furthermore, the focus group discussions revealed that the term "bio-based" is relatively unknown and plays only a minor role in purchasing decisions. Many consumers are not aware of the ecological benefits of bio-based materials, highlighting the importance of clear communication. Future communication measures should therefore convey the term "bio-based" clearly and simply through short explanatory texts, illustrative symbols, or examples directly on the packaging. This can help prevent misunderstandings and build trust. Furthermore, the study by Uehara et al. (2023) shows that acquiring basic knowledge influences consumers' preferences for certain attributes (Uehara et al., 2023). Informational materials can thus help consumers recognize the added value of "bio-based" more quickly and guide their purchasing decisions toward more sustainable products. During the discussion, participants brought up the topic of recycling. It became apparent that information on the recyclability printed directly on the packaging helps consumers perceive the packaging as more sustainable, as "this term is now widely understood", according to one participant. Information on waste separation on packaging is desirable, but it is important that the information on the packaging is easy to understand and strikes a balance between price, quality, and clarity (Hoogland et al., 2007).

In addition to consumers' visual preferences (e.g., colors, uniqueness of design) and the provision of information on the packaging, the material itself also plays a decisive role: regardless of its bio-based origin, plastic is generally perceived as unsustainable. Studies, e.g. Lignou et al. (2021) and Uehara et al. (2023), confirm that it has a negative environmental image compared to other packaging materials (Lignou & Oloyede, 2021; Uehara et al., 2023). This assessment is often based on a general aversion to plastic rather than on sound knowledge of the ecological balance of individual materials. As a result, a potential advantage of bio-based plastics for consumers often remains invisible. This limited perception makes price an even more critical factor in purchasing decisions. A more precise segmentation of participants, for example into "early adopters" or "price-sensitive shoppers", as described in Otto et al. (2021) (Otto et al., 2021), could therefore provide valuable insights into how price sensitivity interacts with the recognition of sustainable packaging benefits. For adoption to increase, it is essential that consumers both clearly perceive the added value of more sustainable packaging and find it reasonably priced.

Figure 2 shows an example of the results of the sorting process conducted by the participants, in which bio-based packaging was assessed in terms of sustainability compared to non-bio-based reference packaging and was then classified into categories ranging from "less sustainable" to "sustainable".

Figure 2: An example of the sorting based on the "Household products" category: new bio-based packaging (prototypes) compared to non-bio-based reference packaging in terms of their sustainability.

Packaging classified as "less sustainable" often has common characteristics. It is mostly small, disposable packaging made of multiple materials, such as plastic and metal, and it features striking

colors, such as pink, orange, and black, for example a cleaning agent bottle that is recognizable as being made of three different materials (bottle body, spout attachment, cap), which are conspicuously colored, and whose bottle body is also labeled. In contrast, packaging rated as "more sustainable" has a simple design and uses a single material consistently. These packages are also characterized by natural colors, such as white, green, or cream/brown, for example a paper cup with a paper lid made of brown cardboard. These results correspond with the findings of Otto et al. (2021) (Otto et al., 2021). Green and brown are associated with sustainable products and low emissions, as are rough textures, like those found in cardboard or paper. Consumers are given the impression of purchasing an environmentally friendly product when labels evoke a connection to nature. This finding is consistent with Bauer et al. (2023), who show that color significantly influences how consumers perceive products (Bauer et al., 2023). To illustrate these observations more concretely, Figure 3 shows the new bio-based packaging (prototypes) rated as most and least sustainable compared to non-bio-based reference packaging.

Figure 3: Summary of all sorting results for the new bio-based packaging (prototypes) and the non-bio-based reference products, showing only the most extreme ratings: packaging rated by participants as less sustainable (left) or most sustainable (right).

The results provide recommendations for increasing the acceptance of new bio-based packaging. The most important recommendations for sustainable labeling of bio-based packaging are a clear explanation of the term "bio-based" and the provision of comprehensive information to consumers. Furthermore, consumers evaluate packaging differently depending on the product group: For cosmetics, design, individuality, and appearance are paramount, while for food, beverages, and household goods, simplicity, functionality, and clearly identifiable sustainability features are most relevant. To increase general acceptance, the price should be comparable to that of conventional packaging.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The study concludes that ecological sustainability must be communicated to consumers clearly and credibly, ideally through a combination of appropriate packaging design and clear labeling. While design elements such as colors or materials can support the intuitive perception of environmental friendliness, clear information on e.g. CO_{2eq} values, recyclability, or recycled content, as required by the new PPWR, is essential to ensure transparency and avoid misunderstandings. For example, clear and simple communication through labels, symbols, or short explanatory texts can be crucial for making the term "bio-based" understandable and enhancing consumer acceptance. Furthermore, careful material selection plays a central role, ideally in the form of recyclable mono-materials, while packaging design is equally important. Consumer expectations and perception patterns must be

specifically addressed. Simple designs, natural colors (e.g., white, green, or cream/brown), and a needs-based selection of packaging sizes (e.g., single vs. family sizes) can positively influence the perception of sustainability. However, this is also the limitation of the study, as it is particularly difficult to separate aesthetic preferences (e.g., colors, design) from the assessment of sustainability, since consumers often intuitively associate visual characteristics with ecological aspects. This overlap should be examined more closely in future studies in order to draw more reliable conclusions. The biggest challenge in the future will be making sustainable packaging recognizable to consumers at first glance. To validate the qualitative findings, a quantitative study will follow, including a 10-minute online survey in Germany, Greece, and Spain, followed by a 15-minute qualitative survey with 10% of participants (n = 15). This study is expected to provide more comprehensive insights into consumer price sensitivity and a deeper understanding of which packaging design features consumers notice and which influence their decision to purchase the product at the point of sale. The study seeks to answer whether consumers truly prefer purchasing products with more sustainable packaging and under which conditions this preference is expressed.

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